

Impact of biochar on anaerobic digestion process and microbiome composition; focusing on pyrolysis conditions for biochar formation

Georgia Vayena^a, Parisa Ghofrani-Isfahani^a, Anastasios Ziomas^a, Antonio Grimalt-Alemany^a, Marie Karen Tracy Hong Lin^b, Giulia Ravenni^a, Iriani Angelidaki^{a,*}

^a Department of Chemical and Biochemical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, Kgs. Lyngby, DK-2800, Denmark

^b National Centre for Nano Fabrication and Characterization, Technical University of Denmark, Kgs. Lyngby, DK-2800, Denmark

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Biogas production
Biochar
Pyrolysis
Methanogenesis
Microbial community

ABSTRACT

This study is a comprehensive investigation of the role of biochar in anaerobic digestion relating various physicochemical properties and the potential biodegradability of biochar to the digestion process. Seven biochars, produced from cedar wood, wheat straw, digestate, and municipal sewage sludge, at temperatures ranging from 400 to 950 °C, were evaluated during mesophilic digestion of cellulose as a model substrate. Pyrolysis conditions significantly affected biochar's properties, with high temperatures resulting in larger surface areas (up to 1262 m²/g) and pore sizes (up to 0.7 cm³/g), more organized graphene-like structures, and higher electrical conductivities. Irrespective of the concentration and diversity of their physicochemical properties, most tested biochars did not affect methane production, despite enriching the relative abundance of the methanogenic community, even up to 42.7 %. Interestingly, wood-based biochar, post-treated by gasification at a high temperature (800 °C), reduced methane yield by up to 52 %. Contrary, methane was increased by 40 % due to residual biodegradable organic matter in biochar produced at a low temperature (400 °C) under incomplete anoxic conditions. This indicates that once the stoichiometric methane potential is reached, no additional methane can be produced by adding biochar, unless it acts as a co-substrate.

1. Introduction

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a key bioengineering technology for the treatment of organic waste. This well-established process provides a sustainable solution for the efficient treatment and valorization of a variety of waste streams into biogas and liquid digestate, thereby enabling bioenergy production and nutrient recovery. Fulfilling the urgent need for renewable energy sources and efficient management of the ever-increasing amounts of organic waste, AD is considered a crucial technology in the implementation of the modern circular bioeconomy [1].

To improve the economy, biogas plants seek methods to increase the biogas potential of the treated waste. Various options have been explored to increase biogas production, including optimization of bioreactor configuration and process parameters, nutrients control, substrate pretreatment, and use of additives such as conductive carbon or iron materials [2,3]. Among these, the addition of biochar, a

low-value conductive carbonaceous material produced by the pyrolysis of biomass, has been increasingly highlighted as an effective method to improve the digestion process [4]. However, a comprehensive comparative study concluding on biochar's properties and their effect on the anaerobic process is still lacking. Compared to other additives, biochar is a highly versatile material with diverse physicochemical properties that vary depending on the feedstock, pyrolysis conditions, and possible post-treatment. Feedstocks range from simple biomass to complex wastes, rendering biochar a promising environmentally and economically effective additive, in line with circular bioeconomy principles [3, 5].

Biochar, exhibiting high specific surface area, porous structure, favorable ion exchange capacity and electrical conductivity, an abundance of functional groups, and alkaline nature, can offer multiple benefits to the digestion process [6]. Its large surface area and porosity can promote microbial immobilization, enhancing microbial interactions, and allow the adsorption of inhibitory compounds. Biochar's

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: geovag@kt.dtu.dk (G. Vayena), parisf@kt.dtu.dk (P. Ghofrani-Isfahani), z.tasos99@gmail.com (A. Ziomas), angral@kt.dtu.dk (A. Grimalt-Alemany), mktracy@dtu.dk (M.K.T.H. Lin), grav@kt.dtu.dk (G. Ravenni), iria@kt.dtu.dk (I. Angelidaki).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.121569>

Received 3 August 2024; Received in revised form 24 September 2024; Accepted 7 October 2024

Available online 9 October 2024

0960-1481/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

alkaline nature makes it an effective pH buffer. Furthermore, it has previously been described that biochar has electron transfer abilities which can potentially facilitate direct interspecies electron transfer (DIET), acting as an electron conduit between electron-donors and electron acceptors [7,8]. Besides, biochar improves the quality of the solid digestate by enhancing nutrient recovery and elemental composition, making digestate an efficient fertilizer and soil improver [7,9].

Numerous previous articles have reported that biochar addition can improve AD performance in terms of stability and efficiency, as evidenced by increased methane yield, production rate, and shorter lag phase [10,11]. Wang et al. [12] showed that gasified corn stalk biochar in the AD of biowaste hydrothermal liquefaction aqueous phase, shortened the lag phase by 11.4 % and increased both the maximum methane yield and production rate by 9.6 % and 16.2 %, respectively. Similarly, Martínez et al. [13] reported that vineyard pruning biochar shortened the lag phase and increased methane production and rate, with a 56 % increase in methane yield in citrus peel waste fermentation. This improvement has been suggested to be a result of pH stabilization, inhibitors adsorption, and DIET facilitation. However, a clear understanding of the multifunctional role of biochar and the relation between its properties and AD outcomes remains unknown. At the same time, some studies reported that biochar lead to biogas yields which were exceeding the maximum stoichiometric methane potential [14], so further research is needed to demystify the potential of biochar-aided AD. In any case, there is a lack of knowledge regarding the potential role of biochar as a biodegradable carbon and nutrients source and its importance in enhancing methane production, particularly at low pyrolysis temperatures.

This study aims to assess the role of biochar in the AD process taking into account the potential biodegradability of biochar. To this end, this work investigates the effect of biochar addition starting from the digestion of cellulose, a model substrate. Biochars from different feedstocks and production methods were evaluated in terms of methane production and residual biodegradable organic content, followed by a thorough characterization of their physicochemical properties. Production temperatures ranged from 400 to 950 °C to evaluate the effect of biochar formation temperature on the AD process. The effect of biochar concentration and the distribution of microbial population during AD cultivations were also studied. The obtained information contributes to the clarification of the function and influence of biochar as a biobased conductive material in the digestion process.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Inoculum characterization

The mesophilic inoculum used in this study came from Hashøj Biogas Plant (Denmark). It was sieved at 1 mm to remove large fibres, sparged with N₂ to ensure anaerobic conditions, and maintained under mesophilic conditions with periodic feeding with cattle manure from the same plant. Prior to use, the inoculum was degassed by incubation at mesophilic conditions (37 ± 1 °C) for 10 days to reduce background biogas production from residual organics in the inoculum. For inoculum's characteristics see [Supplementary Data 1](#).

2.2. Biochar preparation and characterization

Seven types of biochar produced from various feedstocks or under different production conditions were tested. Feedstocks included agricultural and forest byproducts and digested and activated sludge, i.e., readily available materials that require valorization. Cedar wood, wheat straw, digestate, and municipal wastewater sludge, were either pyrolyzed only or also physically activated via gasification, a subsequent thermal treatment of the biochar that increases biochar's specific surface area, porosity and oxygen functional groups [3,15]. Biochar samples were produced at the Technical University of Denmark, Risø Campus.

Dried feedstock was pyrolyzed at 400, 500, or 650 °C in a pilot-scale updraft pyrolysis facility to produce pyrolyzed biochars, except for cedar wood biochar pyrolyzed at 600 °C, which was produced in a lab-scale batch pyrolysis furnace (30 min retention time). Gasified biochar came from the solid residue of the Two-Stage Viking gasifier [16], where dried feedstock underwent pyrolysis at 600 °C followed by gasification at 800 or 950 °C. Biochar samples used in this study were named BC_{S-400}, BC_{S-600}, BC_{S-950}, BC_{W-600}, BC_{W-800}, BC_{D-500}, and BC_{WS-650}, based on their charring temperatures and feedstocks, with numbers representing the treatment temperatures, while the letters BC, S, W, D, and WS the words biochar, straw, wood, digestate, and wastewater sludge, respectively. Prior to use, biochar samples were grinded and sieved to a particle size range of 90–150 μm [11], immersed in distilled water overnight with gentle stirring [17], dried at 105 °C for 24 h, and finally stored in airtight containers until further use.

The elemental composition (CHNS) of the tested biochars was determined using an elemental analyzer (EA3000, Eurovector, Italy). Ash content was determined by complete oxidation at 550 °C for 4 h, and subsequently, oxygen content was calculated by difference. Absolute density was measured using a gas pycnometer (AccuPyc II 1345, Micromeritics, USA). Surface area and porosity were measured by N₂ adsorption at 77 K (NovaTouch, Quantachrome Instruments, USA). The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method was used to calculate the specific surface area and the quenched solid density functional theory (QSDFT) to determine the pore volume on the adsorption branch, assuming slit and cylindrical pores. Porous morphology of the raw biochar was visualized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (FEI Quanta FEG 200, USA). Samples were coated with a 10.8 nm gold layer at 20 mA (Q150T Plus sputter coater, Quorum, UK), and SEM images were captured at 10 kV (spot size of 4, aperture of 20 μm), averaging 16 frames. The pH of the samples was measured by immersing them in 1:10 (w/v) deionized water and gently stirring for 24 h at room temperature. Electrical conductivity (EC) was measured via a custom-made setup as described by Ref. [18], in a pressure range from 21 to 220 kPa.

2.3. Experimental setup

AD batch cultivations were carried out under mesophilic conditions (37 ± 1 °C) using cellulose, as a model substrate with a known chemical structure and an expected theoretical biogas yield, covering all four microbial steps of the AD (theoretical cumulative methane yield: 414.8 mL CH₄/gVS [19]), in the form of Avicel (Avicel® PH-101, Sigma Aldrich). Initially, biochars BC_{S-600}, BC_{S-950}, BC_{W-600}, BC_{W-800}, BC_{D-500}, and BC_{WS-650}, were tested for their impact on the AD of cellulose, with a biochar addition of 15 g/L based on existing literature [11,20]. Complementary experiments were conducted with lower concentrations at 5 and 10 g/L of biochar to assess the effect of biochar concentration. BC_{S-400} was also included in the 5 g/L set, while biochars BC_{D-500} and BC_{WS-650} were excluded from this experimental set due to the inconsistent composition of their feedstock, i.e., digestate and sewage sludge. The composition of these feedstocks can constantly change due to variations in the incoming waste streams, which can produce biochar with varying and unpredictable properties over time. All batch experiments included two types of control, i.e., a control, containing inoculum and substrate, used to monitor the progress of cellulose's digestion, and a set of biochar-controls, containing inoculum and the individual biochars, without substrate, to estimate any potential methane production from the biochar itself. Blank tests, containing only inoculum, were also included to assess the inoculum's background methane production. Methane production measurements, except for biochar-controls' values, were corrected by subtracting the blank's value. Experiments were conducted in 250 mL batch reactors with 100 mL working volume. Water, inoculum, and substrate (if added) were loaded in ratios to achieve a working volume of 20 % inoculation and an initial organic load of 2 gVS/L. The batch reactors were then capped with rubber stoppers and aluminum seals, purged with N₂ gas to ensure anaerobic

conditions, and placed in a shaking mesophilic incubator at 100 rpm. Gas and liquid samples were collected periodically until methane production ceased, to determine biogas composition, pH levels, and volatile fatty acids (VFA) concentration. All reactor conditions were conducted in triplicate, with two reactors for gas production monitoring and one for liquid sampling.

2.4. Analytical methods

pH, total solids (TS), volatile solids (VS), total ammonium nitrogen (TAN), and total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) were measured according to standard methods by ALPHA [21]. Biogas composition was analyzed using a gas chromatograph (GC-TRACE 1310, Thermo Fisher Scientific), equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and a Thermo (P/N 26004–6030) column (30 m length, 0.320 mm inner diameter, 10 μm film thickness), using helium as the carrier gas. VFA were measured, after acidification and centrifugation of the liquid samples, using a gas chromatograph (Agilent 7890 A, Agilent Technologies, US) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and SGE capillary column (30 m length, 0.53 mm inner diameter, 1.00 μm film thickness) with helium as the carrier gas. The injector temperature was maintained at 150 °C and the detector temperature was set at 220 °C. The column oven was initially held at 45 °C for 3.5 min, then ramped up to 210 °C at a rate of 15 °C per minute and held at 210 °C for 4 min. All analytical methods were performed in triplicate with a relative standard deviation not exceeding 5 %.

2.5. Microbial analysis

The microbial community composition of the selected samples was determined using high-throughput 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing. Samples were collected from the control, and batches BC_{S-600}, BC_{S-950}, BC_{W-600}, and BC_{W-800}, with a biochar dosage of 10 g/L, hereinafter referred to as CTRL, BC_{S-600}, BC_{S-950}, BC_{W-600}, BC_{W-800}, as well as samples from BC_{W-800} digesters with biochar dosages of 5 and 15 g/L, hereinafter referred to as BC_{W-800-5} and BC_{W-800-15}. Collection of all samples took place at the end of the incubation period. Samples were initially cleaned using Phenol:Chloroform:Isoamyl alcohol (P:C:IAA-25:24:1, pH = 8), and then DNA was extracted and purified using the DNeasy PowerSoil® Kit (QIAGEN 181 GmbH, Hilden, Germany). DNA quality and quantity were assessed using a Multiskan Sky Microplate Spectrophotometer (operated with Thermo Fisher SkanIt™ Software 5.0, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and a Qubit fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification of 16S rRNA gene V4 hypervariable region was conducted using universal primers 515F/806 R [22] and high throughput sequencing was run through Illumina NovaSeq 6000 platform (2 × 150 bp paired-end sequencing). Raw reads were primer-trimmed with cutadapt, discarding all untrimmed reads [23]. Trimmed reads were quality-filtered, denoised, and merged using DADA2 within the Qiime 2 pipeline (Bolyen et al., 2019). The taxonomic assignment of the amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) was performed using classify-sklearn algorithm and a taxonomic classifier trained on MiDAS 4.81 database using fit-classifier-naive-bayes algorithm [24,25]. Downstream analyses on ASVs were performed using the phyloseq and vegan R packages (Phyloseq version 1.42.0, Vegan version 2.6–4, R version 4.3.2) [26,27].

2.6. Data analysis

The modified Gompertz model was used to simulate the biomethanation process. OriginPro 2023 (OriginLab Corporation, USA) fitted the results using non-linear regression analysis to determine the kinetic parameters and to estimate the prediction accuracy through the coefficient of determination (R^2). One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey post hoc test ($p < 0.05$) was used to detect statistically significant differences using Minitab, LLC (2021).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Biochar properties and their role in AD

When looking at the measured properties of the biochar samples, distinct differences were observed, as well as clear trends between the feedstocks and production methods with property values (Table 1). Specific surface area and total pore volume were closely related and showed the same trend across all samples, with values increasing with increasing production temperature, reaching their highest values in the case of physical activation [3], with BC_{W-800} reaching an SSA of 1262 m²/g and a porosity of 55.61–99.35 % greater than the other samples. SEM analysis showed that biochars' morphology follows the SSA and porosity trend (Supplementary Data 1). Feedstocks treated at higher temperatures resulted in more organized structures and graphene-like carbon layer morphologies [28], as in the case of BC_{W-800}, whereas lower production temperatures produced biochars with morphologies more similar to the original biomass with purer pore formation, as in the case of BC_{S-400}. Low pyrolysis temperatures correlate with low SSA, probably because biochar contains a higher proportion of volatiles and less developed pores, whereas higher temperatures (500–800 °C) would typically result in higher SSA due to the release of volatiles, leaving a porous structure. The formation of micro- and mesopores becomes more pronounced, increasing the total pore volume.

Elemental composition showed a clear correlation in carbon content between the feedstocks, with wood and straw biomass producing a more carbon-rich char than digestate and sludge. This is probably due to the mineralisation of a large portion of carbon during anaerobic digestion and wastewater treatment. The production temperature showed a significant effect, with higher temperatures causing a decrease in H content [29]. BC_{S-400} was characterized by significantly higher H and O contents, with values of 3.3 and 21.7, respectively, a difference also reflected in the H/C (0.69) and O/C (0.29) ratios. Hydrogen to carbon ratio (H/C), a relative measure of aromaticity [29], is feedstock and temperature dependent, with values decreasing with increasing treatment temperatures, while both atomic ratios represent the abundance of hydroxyl and carboxyl functional groups [15], and are positively correlated with the organic content of biochar [30].

The efficiency of electron transfer between microbes, and hence their syntrophic interactions, is largely dependent on electrical conductivity (EC) [7]. EC in carbonaceous materials is related to inherent factors such as carbon content [31], degree of graphitization [32], ash content, and porosity of the structure [18]. Among the materials tested, both BC_{S-400} and BC_{WS-650} showed no EC, a result attributed to their relatively low carbon and high ash content. The remaining samples exhibited EC values consistent with literature trends, with wood biochar and high-temperature biochar exhibiting higher EC values. BC_{W-800} displayed a significantly different behavior, with an EC of 12.68 S/m, a value higher than all other tested materials and results from related studies, due to its graphene-like structure [12,18]. Finally, the pH of all biochar ranged from 6.69 to 10.09, falling within the alkaline range, whereas pH values of samples of common feedstock increased with increasing production temperature.

In an overall comparison of the physicochemical properties of the studied biochars, it was evident that biochars BC_{S-950}, BC_{W-600}, and BC_{W-800} stood out, exhibiting highly favorable properties that could enhance the AD process and even facilitate electron transfer between microorganisms, thereby supporting DIET. The observed differences in biochar properties are expected to result in differences in reaction performance and organic conversion efficiency.

3.2. Effect of biochar addition on methane production

To evaluate the effect of biochar addition and correlate its properties with its function in the AD process, six batch bioreactors with cellulose as substrate were amended with 15 g/L of BC_{S-600}, BC_{S-950}, BC_{W-600},

Table 1
Physicochemical characteristics of tested biochar.

Sample	Absolute density (kg/m ³)	BET surface area (m ² /g)	DFT pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Elemental analysis								pH in solution	Electrical conductivity (S/m) [220 kPa]
				C	H	N	S	O	Ash	O/C	H/C		
				% dwt						Atomic ratio			
BC _{S-400}	1542	2.1	0.0045	56.6 ± 1.2	3.3 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	21.7 ± 1.3	18.4 ± 0.3	0.29 ± 0.1	0.69 ± 0.0	6.69	nd
BC _{S-600}	1596	6.4	0.0099	77.9 ± 1.1	2.0 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.1	<0.1 ± 0.1	4.6 ± 1.2	14.9 ± 0.4	0.04 ± 0.3	0.31 ± 0.0	9.75	0.22
BC _{S-950}	1969	751.9	0.3096	74.0 ± 1.7	0.6 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	11.7 ± 1.7	13.2 ± 0.1	0.12 ± 0.1	0.10 ± 0.1	10.09	5.87
BC _{W-600}	1512	191.5	0.1277	89.5 ± 0.7	2.3 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	<0.1 ± 0.1	6.7 ± 0.7	1.3 ± 0.0	0.06 ± 0.1	0.31 ± 0.0	8.15	7.02
BC _{W-800}	2070	1262.0	0.6974	87.1 ± 6.5	0.5 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	6.5 ± 6.5	5.9 ± 0.2	0.06 ± 1.0	0.07 ± 0.1	9.37	12.68
BC _{D-500}	1773	42.3	0.0340	60.0 ± 1.8	1.6 ± 0.0	1.4 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0	7.4 ± 1.9	29.6 ± 0.2	0.09 ± 0.3	0.32 ± 0.8	7.87	0.36
BC _{WS-650}	2151	53.7	0.0683	24.7 ± 4.2	1.2 ± 0.2	2.8 ± 0.5	0.0 ± 0.0	5.9 ± 4.3	65.4 ± 0.0	0.18 ± 0.8	0.58 ± 0.3	7.90	nd

nd = not detected; dwt = dry weight; ± = standard deviation.

BC_{W-800}, BC_{D-500}, and BC_{WS-650}, respectively. The obtained cumulative methane yields are shown in Fig. 1. The Modified Gompertz model was applied to evaluate the influence of biochar on the kinetic parameters of the AD, and the results are given in Supplementary Data 1. The behavior of biochar BC_{S-600}, BC_{S-950}, BC_{W-600}, BC_{D-500}, and BC_{WS-650} showed no statistically significant differences (Supplementary Data 1), giving slightly lower methane potential, from 9.65 to 17.61 %, than the control. However, BC_{W-800} significantly inhibited AD performance, resulting in a reduction of 52.03 % compared to the control. This behavior could be attributed to the wood feedstock and the high treatment temperature used in the production of BC_{W-800}, and hence potentially released compounds that inhibit the anaerobic digestion process. High-temperature pyrolysis as well as wood feedstocks have been reported to cause the release of harmful substances, such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), phenolics, or heavy metals, leading to biotoxicity [33,34]. In terms of methane production rate, BC_{W-600}, and BC_{D-500} showed increases of 29.81 and 23.60 %, respectively, compared to the control, in contrast to BC_{W-800} and BC_{W-650}, which showed decreases of 7.45 and 11.18 % lower than the control. Finally, all cases tested showed a longer lag phase than the control, with BC_{W-800} showing the longest one, contrary to prior studies suggesting that biochar addition shortens the lag phase [35].

VFA trends (Fig. 2) showed that all biochar-amended batches had similar VFA removal behavior to the control. After 32 days, most of the VFA had been degraded, with the final total VFA concentration being

nullified, a behavior also seen in the inhibitory BC_{W-800}. In all cases, organic acids accumulation remained high until after the end of the lag phase, with total VFA peaks remaining below the inhibition threshold of 1.5 g/L [36]. Overall, biochar addition had no significant effect on VFA consumption, a result consistent with the observed methane production.

The observed behavior of the biochar-amended reactors during cellulose digestion contradicts existing studies. Shanmugam et al. [14] and Wang P. et al. [29] showed that biochar produced at 500 and 400 °C significantly improved AD efficiency during the digestion of glucose, a readily degradable model substrate. They reported reduced lag phases, and increased methane production rates and yields, with yields up to 72 % higher than the theoretical value of the culture control. Despite the simplicity of studied AD systems, they suggested a different biochar behavior to that demonstrated in this study, likely due to differences in biochar production methods, such as low production temperatures and hence residual biodegradable content in biochar (see section 3.4). When testing the same biochars in the digestion of complex organic substrates, Shanmugam et al. [14] and Wang P. et al. [29] observed enhanced methane yields, production rates, and lag phases, with biochars produced at low to medium temperatures improving biogas production more than those produced at higher temperatures. The above cases ascribed the positive effect of biochar to potential interspecies electron transfer (IET) among the microorganisms, however, a similar effect was not verified in this study.

Although biochars tested in this study exhibited subtle physicochemical differences, with some even possessing ideal properties for enhancing the digestion process, no significant differences were observed in their influence. Their addition to the under-investigation AD system did not result in any improvement, but a rather neutral outcome, and in some cases, even had a negative effect, as seen with BC_{W-800}.

3.3. Effect of biochar concentration on methane production

Besides the characteristics of biochar, its effect on AD performance may be concentration dependent. Complementary experiments were conducted using 5 and 10 g/L of biochars BC_{S-600}, BC_{S-950}, BC_{W-600}, and BC_{W-800} (Supplementary Data 1). Results showed no statistically significant differences in maximum methane yield between the two concentrations of BC_{S-600}, BC_{S-950}, and BC_{W-600} biochar samples (Fig. 3). Only BC_{W-800} showed a clear correlation - although negative - between methane production and concentration, with higher concentrations causing more intense inhibition, as discussed in section 3.2. Specifically, at a concentration of 10 g/L, BC_{W-800} showed a maximum methane yield 30.74 % lower than the control, whereas at 5 g/L, the difference was only 13.81 %. This finding confirms the previous assumption that toxic

Fig. 1. Cumulative methane yield at 15 g/L biochar addition.

Fig. 2. Over time effect of 15 g/L biochar addition on total VFA.

Fig. 3. Percentage decrease in methane yield with respect to control for increasing biochar concentration.

compounds may have been generated during the high-temperature pyrolysis and gasification process of woody biomass. Overall, results suggest that the added concentration has little to no effect on the efficiency of methane production, indicating that biochar acts as an inert additive unless harmful compounds are present in the biochar.

3.4. Effect of biodegradable content in biochar structure in the AD

To assess any potential methane production from the biochar itself, a series of tests, the biochar-controls (no substrate addition), were also carried out at all three concentrations and compared to the respective blank tests (inoculum's background methane production). Results from the biochar-controls of the different materials showed minimal additional methane production, regardless of concentration (Fig. 4, Supplementary Data 1). However, a different behavior was observed when the pyrolysis temperature applied was low. This was the case with BC_{S-400}, a wheat straw-based biochar produced at a lower pyrolysis temperature of 400 °C, included in the 5 g/L sets, whose biochar-control assay showed methane production arising for biochar itself (Fig. 4). BC_{S-400} was also the only biochar that produced methane comparable to the control assay when tested in the presence of cellulose (Supplementary Data 1). Given its high H, O content and H/C, O/C ratios (Table 1), which are to be expected for biochars derived from low-temperature pyrolysis (300–500 °C) [7], it can be assumed that BC_{S-400} contains residual biodegradable organic matter, unlike the other tested

Fig. 4. Cumulative methane yield of biochar-controls (no substrate addition) at 5 g/L addition.

biochars which were treated at higher temperatures. This indicates that low pyrolysis temperatures may not be sufficient to fully stabilize the carbon, which can still be subjected to microbial degradation.

Interesting results were also observed when during preliminary tests QBC_{H-400}, a quasi-biochar, i.e., a hemp-derived biochar produced in the laboratory at 400 °C under non-completely anoxic conditions (Q: quasi; H: hemp), was added to the mesophilic digestion of 2 gVS/L cattle manure (inoculum to substrate ratio of 2, biochar dosage of 1 g/L) (Supplementary Data 1). Its biochar-control test resulted in a significant final methane production, 173 % higher than that of the blank, while it also had a clear positive effect on the digestion of the manure, with a final maximum methane yield of almost 40 % higher than that of the corresponding culture control. Just as with BC_{S-400}, the extra production in the QBC_{H-400} was due to the biodegradable biomass contained in the biochar contributing to methane production.

Based on the above, improper pyrolysis conditions, e.g., low pyrolysis temperatures or non-completely anoxic conditions [10,14,20], can result in incomplete carbonization and stabilization of the pyrolyzed biomass [3], leaving biodegradable organic matter in the produced biochar. This residual organic matter could then serve as a substrate, available to microbes, leading to co-digestion with the currently added substrate, and hence to higher methane production and more efficient digestion processes.

3.5. Microbial community composition in biochar-amended bioreactors

16S rRNA analysis was performed to confirm microbial interactions between dominant microbial species in biochar-amended bioreactors. Only community members with relative abundance greater than 0.5 % in at least one sample were considered. 71 amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) were selected for further analysis, representing 76–85 % of the ASVs in the samples. Taxonomic assignments, relative abundances and abundance changes in terms of fold change are available in [Supplementary Data 2](#).

3.5.1. Microbial community profiles of the different biochar-amended digesters

The microbial composition of the biochar-amended reactors should reflect the results of biomethanation. To confirm this, microbial samples from batches amended with four different biochars at a concentration of 10 g/L were compared with the control, with their relative abundance and fold change shown in [Supplementary Data 1](#). Alpha diversity analysis and Shannon index revealed similar microbial diversity in all reactors, including the control, with values above 4.5, signifying high microbial diversity ([Supplementary Data 1](#)). Principal coordinates analysis (PCoA) ([Fig. 5](#)) showed a distinct microbial composition in BC_{W-800} compared to other samples, which clustered with the control, suggesting that reductions in methane production could stem from microbial community differences. Meanwhile, the unexpected separation of BC_{S-950} from the cluster indicated that its addition caused a microbial shift, which, however, did not affect the methane yield.

In the bacterial domain, BC_{W-800} showed significant variations in the relative abundances of Firmicutes and Synergistota. Both phyla have members known for their ability to act as syntrophic acetate oxidizers (SAO) [37,38]. The Firmicutes are also known to hydrolyze poly- and oligosaccharides [37], whereas the Synergistota degrade amino acids, providing valuable substrates such as hydrogen, carbon dioxide, and acetate to methanogenic archaea [39], and thus performing crucial functions for the output of the digestion process. In the Firmicutes phylum, *Acholeplasma* sp. DTU28 was absent from BC_{W-800}, unlike the other bioreactors. In contrast, the BC_{W-800} sample showed a higher abundance of Anaerovoracaceae sp. DTU60, *Herbinix luporum* DTU34, and a potential SAO MBA03 sp. DTU29 [40]. In Synergistota, Synergistaceae sp. DTU26 exhibited a high decrease in abundance in BC_{W-800} compared to the control, despite the enrichment in the remaining samples.

Significant differences were also observed between the bioreactors in

Fig. 5. Principal coordinates analysis (PCoA) plot representing the microbial distribution at family level of the most abundant ASVs in samples BC_{S-600}, BC_{S-950}, BC_{W-600}, and BC_{W-800} at 10 g/L biochar addition.

the archaeal domain. The overall lower abundance of methanogens in the control reactor without biochar, which was 4.3–42.7 % lower than in the biochar-amended reactors, shows that biochar addition enriched the methanogenic population. It should be noted, though, that the values here represent the relative and not the absolute abundance of microbes. Therefore, the higher methanogenic abundance can also be interpreted as a higher toxicity of biochar to bacteria compared to archaeal species. There were also exceptions to this trend, i.e. an increase in the representation of methanogens in biochar amended reactors, with methanogens in BC_{W-800} accounting for only 11.4 % of all species present, 18 % less than in the control. This coincided with the lower methane yield of the BC_{W-800}-amended reactor, which could be partly attributed to the inhibition of the methanogenic community. This could also support that BC_{W-800}, a biochar produced from wood biomass at high temperatures, could contain inhibitory compounds for the anaerobic digestion process. In all samples, acetoclastic methanogenesis was mainly performed by *Methanosarcina*, a genus known for its versatility in utilizing all three methanogenic pathways, i.e., hydrogenotrophic, acetoclastic, and methylotrophic [41], although most strains are mainly acetoclastic [42]. In contrast, species belonging to the *Methanothermobacter*, *Methanobacterium*, and *Methanoculleus* genera are strictly hydrogenotrophic [43,44]. The addition of straw biochar BC_{S-950} shifted the methanogenic community, rendering hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis the primary pathway, with a total abundance of 14.08 % compared to 5.81 % for *Methanosarcina*. This shift is also confirmed by the enriched presence of the aforementioned SAOs and other syntrophic hydrogen-producing bacteria such as *Desulfosporosinus* sp. DTU47, a bacterium that likely oxidized acetate syntrophically with hydrogenotrophic archaea, out-competing acetoclasts [45,46].

Overall, the coexistence of SAOs with members of the methanogenic community could lead to syntrophic interactions, possibly based on DIET [47]. Species in the *Methanobacterium* genus, such as *Methanobacterium formicicum* DTU17, are known to support syntrophic interactions with acetogens performing interspecies hydrogen transfer (IHT) [44], while members of the genus *Methanosarcina* (e.g. *Methanosarcina barkeri*) can interact with syntrophic partners and perform DIET [48]. Given the abilities of these methanogenic species and the high EC values observed in some of the tested biochar ([Table 1](#)), the possibility of the DIET mechanism could not be ruled out.

3.5.2. Microbial community shifts with dosage variation of inhibitory BC_{W-800}

The wood-derived biochar BC_{W-800}, produced by a two-step pyrolysis (600 °C) and gasification (800 °C) process, inhibited AD. To understand this inhibition at a microbial level, microbial samples were collected and analyzed from reactors containing 5, 10, and 15 g/L of BC_{W-800}. Alpha diversity analysis using the Shannon index revealed variations in microbial diversity at different doses ([Supplementary Data 1](#)). Although BC_{W-800-5} had a similar index (4.6) to both BC_{W-800-10} and CTRL, BC_{W-800-15} had a lower value (3.9), indicating lower microbial diversity and an uneven species distribution. Taxonomic analysis identified the Firmicutes, Bacteroidota, and Euryarchaeota phyla as the most dominant in all three samples, although their abundance varied significantly across samples ([Supplementary Data 1](#)).

A correlation analysis between the added concentration and microbial activity in BC_{W-800} reactors ([Fig. 6, Supplementary Data 1](#)) revealed that Firmicutes and Bacteroidota were positively correlated with concentration, with Firmicutes sp. DTU8, Bacteroidales sp. DTU49 and Dysgonomonadaceae sp. DTU22 showing a significant increase in abundance with biochar dosage. Conversely, Synergistota presented ASVs that were negatively correlated with added concentration, such as *Thermovigra* sp. DTU59 which decreased from a relative abundance of 0.54 % at 5 g/L to 0.06 % at 15 g/L. Significant negative correlations were also found for Pirellulaceae sp. DTU6, *Corynebacterium humir-educens* DTU15, and Candidatus Cloacimonadales DTU16. Most of the correlations in the archaeal domain were negative, explaining the

Fig. 6. Correlation plot of microbial species with biochar concentration and methane yield. The plot presents species found in the BC_{W-800} digesters that showed a statistically significant correlation ($p < 0.05$ %) of at least 70 % with varying additive concentrations.

overall decline of the Euryarchaeota with increasing concentration, consistent with the observed methane results. Hydrogenotrophic methanogens, such as *Methanobacterium* sp. DTU9, showed a negative correlation with concentration. In contrast, mixotrophs showed no clear correlation with dosage, with *Methanosarcina* sp. DTU3 and *Methanosarcina thermophila* DTU51 showing negative and positive correlations, respectively.

Although the methanogenic content of BC_{W-800-10} and BC_{W-800-15} is significantly decreased compared to BC_{W-800-5} (negative variation > 20 %), the variance between the two samples is very low (3.57 %). This difference, however, is not reflected in the corresponding methane yields where the inhibition is more pronounced in BC_{W-800-15}. This suggests that BC_{W-800} was not exclusively inhibiting methanogens but also bacteria from earlier stages of the anaerobic process, reducing organic matter degradation and available methanogenic substrates. A characteristic example is *Thermovirga* sp. DTU59, which as previously noted, had a strong negative correlation with increasing concentration. This acidogenic bacterium accelerates hydrolysis and acidogenesis by fermenting specific amino and organic acids, producing end products essential for methanogens [12,49].

4. Conclusions

The present study provides a comprehensive analysis of the effect of biochar on mesophilic anaerobic digestion. Biochars from different feedstocks and production conditions, with significant variations in their physicochemical properties, included biochars with properties highly favorable to the AD process. Most of the tested biochars showed no

positive effect on methane yield, regardless of the concentration added. In contrast, wood-based biochar (BC_{W-800}) post-treated by high-temperature gasification (800 °C) inhibited the biogas process with a 52 % methane reduction at 15 g/L addition, alongside an 18 % reduction in methanogens and a general decrease in microbial diversity. Finally, additional methane yield was observed when using biochar containing residual biodegradable organic matter due to low-temperature and incomplete pyrolysis (BC_{S-400}, QBC_{H-400}). Biochar comprises a diverse group of carbon materials and its properties are largely dependent on the pyrolysis conditions. Pyrolysis at high temperatures can potentially lead to the release or production of toxic compounds that inhibit the digestion process, while low pyrolysis temperatures may not fully stabilize the pyrolyzed biomass, resulting in biochar that contributes to methane production through its content of biodegradable organic matter. In any case, upon the complete biomethanation of the substrate, the addition of well-stabilized biochar cannot lead to additional methane regardless of its improved physicochemical properties.

Data availability

All study data are included in the article and/or supplementary material. Sequence data are deposited at NCBI-SRA as BioProject PRJNA1096949. Further information will be made available on request.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Georgia Vayena: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology,

Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Parisa Ghofrani-Isfahani**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Anastasios Ziomas**: Investigation. **Antonio Grimalt-Alemany**: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Marie Karen Tracy Hong Lin**: Investigation. **Giulia Ravenni**: Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Irini Angelidaki**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Funding

This work was supported by the Novo Nordisk Foundation under the project framework DIET-Syntrophy “Direct interspecies electron transfer-based syntrophic metabolism between sulfate-reducing bacteria and methanogens via conductive materials” [program No. NNF21OC007139]; and the European Union’s HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01 under the project framework FENIX “New Life for Biowaste as a Sustainable Soil Improver” [grant agreement No. 101113002].

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.121569>.

References

- [1] T. Magnusson, H. Zanatta, M. Larsson, W. Kanda, O. Hjelm, Circular economy, varieties of capitalism and technology diffusion: anaerobic digestion in Sweden and Paraná, *J. Clean. Prod.* 335 (2022) 130300 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.130300>.
- [2] L. Chen, W. Fang, J. Chang, J. Liang, P. Zhang, G. Zhang, Improvement of direct interspecies electron transfer via adding conductive materials in anaerobic digestion: mechanisms, performances, and challenges, *Front. Microbiol.* 13 (2022) 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.860749>.
- [3] M. Chiappero, O. Norouzi, M. Hu, F. Demichelis, F. Berruti, F. Di Maria, O. Mašek, S. Fiore, Review of biochar role as additive in anaerobic digestion processes, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 131 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110037>.
- [4] M. Chen, S. Liu, X. Yuan, Q.X. Li, F. Wang, F. Xin, B. Wen, Methane production and characteristics of the microbial community in the co-digestion of potato pulp waste and dairy manure amended with biochar, *Renew. Energy* 163 (2021) 357–367, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.09.006>.
- [5] H. Liu, X. Wang, Y. Fang, W. Lai, S. Xu, E. Lichtfouse, Enhancing thermophilic anaerobic co-digestion of sewage sludge and food waste with biogas residue biochar, *Renew. Energy* 188 (2022) 465–475, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.02.044>.
- [6] W. Zhao, H. Yang, S. He, Q. Zhao, L. Wei, A review of biochar in anaerobic digestion to improve biogas production: performances, mechanisms and economic assessments, *Bioresour. Technol.* 341 (2021) 125797, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2021.125797>.
- [7] M. Kumar, S. Dutta, S. You, G. Luo, S. Zhang, P.L. Show, A.D. Sawarkar, L. Singh, D. C.W. Tsang, A critical review on biochar for enhancing biogas production from anaerobic digestion of food waste and sludge, *J. Clean. Prod.* 305 (2021) 127143, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127143>.
- [8] A.R. Salehiyoun, H. Zilouei, M. Safari, F. Di Maria, S.H. Samadi, O. Norouzi, An investigation for improving dry anaerobic digestion of municipal solid wastes by adding biochar derived from gasification of wood pellets, *Renew. Energy* 186 (2022) 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.12.115>.
- [9] C. Zhang, G. Zeng, D. Huang, C. Lai, M. Chen, M. Cheng, W. Tang, L. Tang, H. Dong, B. Huang, X. Tan, R. Wang, Biochar for environmental management: mitigating greenhouse gas emissions, contaminant treatment, and potential negative impacts, *Chem. Eng. J.* 373 (2019) 902–922, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.05.139>.
- [10] G. Wang, X. Gao, Q. Li, H. Zhao, Y. Liu, X.C. Wang, R. Chen, Redox-based electron exchange capacity of biowaste-derived biochar accelerates syntrophic phenol oxidation for methanogenesis via direct interspecies electron transfer, *J. Hazard Mater.* 390 (2020) 121726, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.121726>.
- [11] L. Zhang, E.Y. Lim, K.C. Loh, Y.S. Ok, J.T.E. Lee, Y. Shen, C.H. Wang, Y. Dai, Y. W. Tong, Biochar enhanced thermophilic anaerobic digestion of food waste: focusing on biochar particle size, microbial community analysis and pilot-scale application, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 209 (2020) 112654, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2020.112654>.
- [12] Z. Wang, C. Zhang, J. Watson, B.K. Sharma, B. Si, Y. Zhang, Adsorption or direct interspecies electron transfer? A comprehensive investigation of the role of biochar in anaerobic digestion of hydrothermal liquefaction aqueous phase, *Chem. Eng. J.* 435 (2022) 135078, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.135078>.
- [13] E.J. Martínez, J.G. Rosas, A. Sotres, A. Moran, J. Cara, M.E. Sánchez, X. Gómez, Codigestion of sludge and citrus peel wastes: evaluating the effect of biochar addition on microbial communities, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 137 (2018) 314–325, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2018.06.010>.
- [14] S.R. Shanmugam, S. Adhikari, H. Nam, S. Kar Sajib, Effect of bio-char on methane generation from glucose and aqueous phase of algae liquefaction using mixed anaerobic cultures, *Biomass Bioenergy* 108 (2018) 479–486, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2017.10.034>.
- [15] H. Li, X. Dong, E.B. da Silva, L.M. de Oliveira, Y. Chen, L.Q. Ma, Mechanisms of metal sorption by biochars: biochar characteristics and modifications, *Chemosphere* 178 (2017) 466–478, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.03.072>.
- [16] J. Ahrenfeldt, T.P. Thomsen, U. Henriksen, L.R. Clausen, Biomass gasification cogeneration - a review of state of the art technology and near future perspectives, in: *Appl. Therm. Eng.*, Elsevier Ltd, 2013, pp. 1407–1417, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2011.12.040>.
- [17] M. Yan, X. Zhu, L. Treu, G. Ravenni, S. Campanaro, E.M. Goonesekera, R. Ferrigno, C.S. Jacobsen, A. Zervas, I. Angelidaki, I.A. Fotidis, Comprehensive evaluation of different strategies to recover methanogenic performance in ammonia-stressed reactors, *Bioresour. Technol.* 336 (2021) 125329, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2021.125329>.
- [18] Z. Li, G. Ravenni, H. Bi, C.E. Weinell, B. Ulusoy, Y. Zhang, K. Dam-Johansen, Effects of biochar nanoparticles on anticorrosive performance of zinc-rich epoxy coatings, *Prog. Org. Coating* 158 (2021) 106351, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.porgcoat.2021.106351>.
- [19] I. Angelidaki, W. Sanders, Assessment of the anaerobic biodegradability of macropollutants, *Rev. Environ. Sci. Biotechnol.* 3 (2004) 117–129, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11157-004-2502-3>.
- [20] G. Wang, Q. Li, X. Gao, X.C. Wang, Synergetic promotion of syntrophic methane production from anaerobic digestion of complex organic wastes by biochar: performance and associated mechanisms, *Bioresour. Technol.* 250 (2018) 812–820, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.12.004>.
- [21] R.B. Baird, A.D. Eaton, E.W. Rice (Eds.), *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*, 23rd ed., American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, Water Environment Federation, Washington, DC, 2017.
- [22] J.G. Caporaso, C.L. Lauber, W.A. Walters, D. Berg-Lyons, C.A. Lozupone, P. J. Turnbaugh, N. Fierer, R. Knight, Global patterns of 16S rRNA diversity at a depth of millions of sequences per sample, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 108 (2011) 4516–4522, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.100080107>.
- [23] M. Marcel, Cutadapt removes adapter sequences from high-throughput sequencing reads, *EMBnet.J.* 17 (2011) 10–12, <https://doi.org/10.14806/ebj.17.1.200>.
- [24] E. Bolyen, J.R. Rideout, M.R. Dillon, et al., Reproducible, interactive, scalable and extensible microbiome data science using QIIME 2, *Nat. Biotechnol.* 37 (2019) 852–857, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-019-0209-9>.
- [25] M.K.D. Dueholm, M. Nierychlo, K.S. Andersen, et al., MIDAS 4: a global catalogue of full-length 16S rRNA gene sequences and taxonomy for studies of bacterial communities in wastewater treatment plants, *Nat. Commun.* 13 (2022) 1–15, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-29438-7>.
- [26] P.J. McMurdie, S. Holmes, Phyloseq: an R package for reproducible interactive analysis and graphics of microbiome census data, *PLoS One* 8 (2013), <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0061217>.
- [27] Vegan, GitHub - vegandevs/vegan, R package for community ecologists: popular ordination methods, ecological null models & diversity analysis. <https://github.com/vegandevs/vegan>, 2023. (Accessed 20 June 2024).
- [28] A. Tomczyk, Z. Sokolowska, P. Boguta, Biochar physicochemical properties: pyrolysis temperature and feedstock kind effects, *Rev. Environ. Sci. Biotechnol.* 19 (2020) 191–215, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11157-020-09523-3>.
- [29] P. Wang, H. Peng, S. Adhikari, B. Higgins, P. Roy, W. Dai, X. Shi, Enhancement of biogas production from wastewater sludge via anaerobic digestion assisted with biochar amendment, *Bioresour. Technol.* 309 (2020) 123368, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2020.123368>.
- [30] L. Wei, Y. Huang, L. Huang, Y. Li, Q. Huang, G. Xu, K. Müller, H. Wang, Y.S. Ok, Z. Liu, The ratio of H/C is a useful parameter to predict adsorption of the herbicide metolachlor to biochars, *Environ. Res.* 184 (2020) 109324, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109324>.
- [31] V. Hoffmann, C. Rodriguez Correa, D. Sautter, E. Maringolo, A. Kruse, Study of the electrical conductivity of biobased carbonaceous powder materials under moderate pressure for the application as electrode materials in energy storage technologies, *GCB Bioenergy* 11 (2019) 230–248, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.12545>.
- [32] S. Shi, X. Zhou, W. Chen, M. Chen, T. Nguyen, X. Wang, W. Zhang, Improvement of structure and electrical conductivity of activated carbon by catalytic graphitization using N₂ plasma pretreatment and iron(III) loading, *RSC Adv.* 7 (2017) 44632–44638, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7ra07328c>.
- [33] P. Godlewska, Y.S. Ok, P. Oleszczuk, The dark side of black gold: ecotoxicological aspects of biochar and biochar-amended soils, *J. Hazard Mater.* 403 (2021) 123833, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.123833>.
- [34] İ.A. Başar, C. Eskicioglu, N.A. Perendeci, Biochar and wood ash amended anaerobic digestion of hydrothermally pretreated lignocellulosic biomass for biorefinery applications, *Waste Manag.* 154 (2022) 350–360, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2022.10.014>.
- [35] N.M.S. Sunyoto, M. Zhu, Z. Zhang, D. Zhang, Effect of biochar addition on hydrogen and methane production in two-phase anaerobic digestion of aqueous

- carbohydrates food waste, *Bioresour. Technol.* 219 (2016) 29–36, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.07.089>.
- [36] I. Angelidaki, K. Boe, L. Ellegaard, Effect of operating conditions and reactor configuration on efficiency of full-scale biogas plants, *Water Sci. Technol.* 52 (2005) 189–194, <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2005.0516>.
- [37] S. Dykstra, L. Jansen, C. Gallert, Syntrophic acetate oxidation replaces acetoclastic methanogenesis during thermophilic digestion of biowaste, *Microbiome* 8 (2020) 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-020-00862-5>.
- [38] M. Gao, B. Guo, L. Li, Y. Liu, Role of syntrophic acetate oxidation and hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis in co-digestion of blackwater with food waste, *J. Clean. Prod.* 283 (2021) 125393, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125393>.
- [39] L.E.X. Leong, S.E. Denman, P. Hugenholtz, C.S. Mcsweeney, Amino acid and peptide utilization profiles of the fluoroacetate-degrading bacterium synergistetes strain MFA1 under varying conditions, *Microb. Ecol.* 71 (2016) 494–504, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-015-0641-4>.
- [40] J. Moestedt, E. Perman, Serial anaerobic digestion improves protein degradation and biogas production from mixed food waste, *Biomass Bioenergy* (2022) 161, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2022.106478>.
- [41] A. Conklin, H.D. Stensel, J. Ferguson, Growth kinetics and competition between *Methanosarcina* and *methanosaeta* in mesophilic anaerobic digestion, *Water Environ. Res.* 78 (2006), <https://doi.org/10.2175/106143006X95393>.
- [42] B. Demirel, P. Scherer, The roles of acetotrophic and hydrogenotrophic methanogens during anaerobic conversion of biomass to methane: a review, *Rev. Environ. Sci. Biotechnol.* 7 (2008) 173–190, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11157-008-9131-1>.
- [43] A.J.M. Stams, K.C.F. Grolle, C.T.M.J. Frijters, J.B. Van Lier, Enrichment of thermophilic propionate-oxidizing bacteria in syntrophy with *Methanobacterium thermoautotrophicum* or *Methanobacterium thermoformicum*, *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 58 (1992) 346–352, <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.58.1.346-352.1992>.
- [44] L. Treu, P.G. Kougias, B. De Diego-díaz, S. Campanaro, I. Bassani, *Bioresour. Technol.* Two-year microbial adaptation during hydrogen-mediated biogas upgrading process in a serial reactor configuration, *Bioresour. Technol.* 264 (2018) 140–147, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2018.05.070>.
- [45] I. Sánchez-Andrea, C.M. van der Graaf, B. Hornung, N.J. Bale, M. Jarzembowska, D.Z. Sousa, W.I.C. Rijpstra, J.S. Sinninghe Damsté, A.J.M. Stams, Acetate degradation at low pH by the moderately acidophilic sulfate reducer *acididesulfobacillus acetoxydans* gen. Nov. sp. nov., *Front. Microbiol.* 13 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.816605>.
- [46] A. da Silva Martins, B. Ornelas Ferreira, N.C. Ribeiro, R. Martins, L. Rabelo Leite, G. Oliveira, L.F. Colturato, C.A. Chernicharo, J.C. de Araujo, Metagenomic analysis and performance of a mesophilic anaerobic reactor treating food waste at various load rates, *Environ. Technol.* 38 (2017) 2153–2163, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2016.1247197>.
- [47] A. Damodara, P. Evans, P. Parameswaran, *Bioresour. Technol.* Long-term microbial community dynamics in a pilot-scale gas sparged anaerobic membrane bioreactor treating municipal wastewater under seasonal variations, *Bioresour. Technol.* 310 (2020) 123425, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2020.123425>.
- [48] X. Zhu, S. Campanaro, L. Treu, R. Seshadri, N. Ivanova, P.G. Kougias, N. Kyrpides, I. Angelidaki, Metabolic dependencies govern microbial syntrophies during methanogenesis in an anaerobic digestion ecosystem, *Microbiome* 8 (2020) 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-019-0780-9>.
- [49] H. Dahle, N.K. Birkeland, *Thermovirga lienii* gen. nov., sp. nov., a novel moderately thermophilic, anaerobic, amino-acid-degrading bacterium isolated from a North Sea oil well, *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* 56 (2006) 1539–1545, <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijs.0.63894-0>.